

Press Releases

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01 Gridded Ion Engine Propulsion System to boost Europe's competitiveness in the global satellite market

February 25, 2021

Gridded Ion Engine Standardised Electric Propulsion Platform (GIESEPP), operating ArianeGroup ion engines with the option of alternative thrusters, continues to develop within the GIESEPP MP project funded by the Horizon 2020 framework programme of the European Union.

Electric propulsion offers major improvements in fuel efficiency over chemical propulsion systems, enabling dramatic weight and volume savings, reduced launcher costs, and higher revenues for operators due to the increase in payload that electric propulsion facilitates. A state-of-the-art European gridded ion engine will give Europe the ability to not only compete but also take a lead in this growing worldwide market. The market volume is expected to grow from one-off sales to at least double-digit systems per year across telecommunications, navigation and scientific satellites.

In practice, this means that the weight and volume of heavy GEO satellites can be reduced considerably to allow for more payload such as additional transponders. At the same time, tiny LEO satellites can allow for a high-end propulsion system without losing their assets for launchers.

The project aims to continue the developments of the previously funded project GIESEPP (Gridded Ion Engine Standardised Electric Propulsion Platform), which sought to build and test a modular propulsion solution to a technical readiness level of TRL5 (Technology validated in relevant environment) in its different configurations for LEO, GEO and space exploration missions. The restructured consortium will demonstrate and pre-qualify a prototype-like system in a relevant environment up to TRL 6/7.

According to project coordinator Cyril Dietz, ArianeGroup GmbH: *“The modular approach, which allows for both scaling in power levels and the interchangeability of core components, has already encountered worldwide interest. Thus, we are looking forward to approving it with the key players in the community and proceeding to market with it.”*

The GIESEPP MP project consortium

The GIESEPP MP project will be implemented by a consortium comprising ArianeGroup GmbH (Germany), which will provide thruster engineering and project coordination; Airbus Defence & Space (France) for mission requirements and systems engineering; Aerospazio Tecnologie s.r.l. (Italy) as system testing experts; Justus-Liebig Universität Gießen (Germany), which will take care of thruster level tests and scientific support; CRISA (Spain), which will be in charge of the power processing unit; and WIT Berry (Latvia) for all communication and dissemination purposes. The project duration is 3 years. The project started in January 2021 with a successful kick-off.

GIESEPP – highest efficiency in every mission.

02 The future of space propulsion: GIESEPP MP project concludes with breakthroughs in cost-effective communication satellite technology

November 29, 2024

The GIESEPP MP project, co-funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 programme, is set to conclude in December 2024, marking a pivotal milestone in the development of advanced electric propulsion systems for space applications. Building on the groundwork of the earlier GIESEPP project (Gridded Ion Engine Standardised Electric Propulsion Platform), the restructured consortium successfully demonstrated the operability of a prototype-like system in a relevant environment, and fully validated the operating points of GIESEPP MP, setting new standards for efficiency and performance.

A key highlight was the final Electric Propulsion System (EPS) coupling test campaign, conducted at Aerospazio Tecnologie's cutting-edge LVTF-3 vacuum facility in Italy. The campaign brought together the ArianeGroup RIT2X thruster, Airbus Crisa's PPU, and Airbus-DS fluidic regulator to validate the functional performance of the coupled Electric Propulsion System. Covering mission-critical phases such as orbit raising and station keeping, the tests characterized the RIT2X thruster's plume and provided important data on thrust, divergence, ion energy and other performance metrics.

The project also incorporated a market assessment conducted by Airbus, which revealed promising opportunities for the technology developed under GIESEPP MP. Specifically, GEO, communication satellites and space exploration missions stand to benefit significantly from the advancements, with the potential for important mass savings and propulsion function cost optimization, used for satellite transfer and operation phases

The RIT2X thruster, developed by ArianeGroup Germany, exemplifies cutting-edge propulsion technology. One of the largest Radiofrequency Ion Thrusters ever created, it leverages Xenon gas to produce thrust through ionization and electrostatic acceleration, supported by Airbus Crisa's Power Processing Unit (PPU), which ensures precise management and operation.

Christian Knorr, ArianeGroup Project Manager & GIESEPP MP Consortium Coordinator “With the successful completion of GIESEPP MP Europe has made an enormous step forward towards high ISP electric propulsion systems. In parallel to the product maturation and validation activities, industrial scale series production has been prepared and we will soon be able to serve the European and worldwide market with outstanding electric propulsion products.”

As the GIESEPP MP project concludes, the consortium members are committed to leveraging the knowledge gained and exploring new applications of this technology as they move forward to deliver the final product to the market.

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